

Rigorous simulation of opto-mechanically modulated electromagnetic micro- and nano-cavities

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Abstract— In this contribution, we report on numerical simulation of a multi-physic Electromagnetic/Mechanical problem, as a further step towards the development of GHz circuits based on phonon propagation at micro-and nano-scale. In the future, this kind of circuits is likely to integrate opto-mechanically pumped phonon sources and detectors, as well as phonon processing components (waveguides, splitters, memories) to process information by means of phonons. In particular, we propose a rigorous approach for the solution of the electromagnetic/mechanical system of equations governing light behavior in opto-mechanical cavities, with the help of the Transformation Optics (TO) method. Such kind of calculation allows the development of an efficient generation of GHz to tens of GHz coherent phonon sources, by engineering their propagation or coupling with phonon waveguides.

I. INTRODUCTION

The interplay of mechanical vibrational modes and confined electromagnetic fields in opto-mechanical (OM) cavities constitutes a challenging problem, from the simulation point of view, due to its intrinsic multiphysic and multiscale nature. This complexity can lead to unexpected and useful, even non linear, effects [1,2]. In the last years, the emerging field of OM cavities has brought about several breakthroughs that would enable on-chip photonic-operated phononic circuits to become a reality [3-5]. In particular, optically-driven sources of coherent phonons, phonon lasers albeit at low temperatures, have been demonstrated up to a few GHz. Such a frequency range allows straightforward manipulation of radio frequency (RF) signals, otherwise not easily attainable by electrical means with, e.g., interdigitated transducers (IDT). An important advantage here is the wavelength of the relevant phonons (tens to 100s nm at 300 K), which will lead to further miniaturisation. Moreover, compared to pure nano electromechanical actuation, the OM approach does not suffer from capacitive nor impedance mismatch problems. The analytical treatment of micro- and nano-OM cavities relies on the coupling between the two ruling equations of, respectively, the continuum mechanics and the electromagnetism [6]. The theoretical foundation of the problem under consideration is described in the next section.

II. THEORETICAL BASIS

Starting from the mechanical equations, the Lagrangian coordinates-based balance of linear momentum is modified by the presence of a EM-field as:

$$\rho_0 \Omega^2 \mathbf{u} + \nabla_{\mathbf{x}} \cdot (\bar{\mathbf{F}} \bar{\mathbf{S}}) = -\mathbf{F}_{ES,V} \quad (1)$$

where ρ_0 is the mass density of the undeformed configuration, Ω the acoustic wave frequency, $\bar{\mathbf{F}}$ the deformation gradient tensor, $\bar{\mathbf{S}}$ the second Piola-Kirchhoff tensor, $\nabla_{\mathbf{x}}$ the nabla in Lagrangian coordinates, and

$$\mathbf{F}_{ES,V} = f_x^{ES,V} \hat{x} + f_y^{ES,V} \hat{y} + f_z^{ES,V} \hat{z},$$

$$f_x^{ES,V} = -\partial_x \sigma_{xx} - \partial_y \sigma_{xy} - \partial_z \sigma_{xz},$$

$$f_y^{ES,V} = -\partial_x \sigma_{xy} - \partial_y \sigma_{yy} - \partial_z \sigma_{yz},$$

$$f_z^{ES,V} = -\partial_x \sigma_{xz} - \partial_y \sigma_{yz} - \partial_z \sigma_{zz}$$

is the electrostrictive force of the E-field components oscillating at different angular frequencies ω_1 (pumped E-field) and ω_2 (scattered E-field), with the latter found as $\omega_2 = \omega_1 - \Omega$, where ϵ_1 is the dielectric constant of the cavity, ϵ_2 the dielectric constant of the surrounding domain and $\bar{\sigma}$ is the electrostriction tensor, defined as

$$\sigma_{ij} = -\frac{1}{2} \epsilon_0 \epsilon_1^2 p_{ijkl} E_k E_l$$

in which we consider the strain-optic tensor p_{ijkl} .

For simplicity, boundary forces, like radiation pressure, are neglected in this context, but they can be easily included in the model. Passing to the Helmholtz equations, the acoustic wave causes a relative permittivity variation of the form

$$\bar{\Delta \epsilon} = -\sum_{kl} \epsilon_1^2 p_{ijkl} \epsilon_{kl},$$

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where ϵ_{kl} is the strain tensor. The just reported contribute introduces a perturbation on the polarizability $\mathbf{P}_i$, i.e. the following source terms:

$$\nabla^2 \mathbf{E}_1 + k_1^2 \mathbf{E}_1 = -\mu_0 \omega_1^2 \mathbf{P}_1 = -\mu_0 \omega_1^2 \frac{\epsilon_0}{2} \Delta \epsilon \mathbf{E}_2 \quad (2)$$

$$\nabla^2 \mathbf{E}_2 + k_2^2 \mathbf{E}_2 = -\mu_0 \omega_2^2 \mathbf{P}_2 = -\mu_0 \omega_2^2 \frac{\epsilon_0}{2} \Delta \epsilon^* \mathbf{E}_1 \quad (3)$$

where k_i denotes the wave numbers of the two monochromatic EM-waves. Situation is schematically depicted in Fig. 1.

Such a coupling process, although analytically straightforward, requires further considerations in order to be implemented in a full-wave solver. This is because the Eulerian environment in which the Helmholtz equations are solved is not able to account for the movement of the geometry, arising from the existence of displacements. The latter are numerically significant in the case of micro- and nano-scale cavities.

Fig. 1. Electro-Mechanical interaction in a micron or submicron scale cavity results in frequency and wavenumber modulation of the electromagnetic field.

The above problem can be addressed by the Transformation Optics (TO) method [7], which basically models the movement of the material points at the boundaries of the considered domain by an effective time-oscillation of electromagnetic properties μ and ϵ_1 :

$$\bar{\bar{\epsilon}} = \frac{\bar{\bar{F}} \bar{\bar{F}}^T}{\det \bar{\bar{F}}} \epsilon_1 = \bar{\bar{g}} \epsilon_1$$

$$\bar{\bar{\mu}} = \frac{\bar{\bar{F}} \bar{\bar{F}}^T}{\det \bar{\bar{F}}} \mu = \bar{\bar{g}} \mu$$

Here, the deformation gradient $\bar{\bar{F}}$ assumes the parts of the Jacobian matrix associated to the coordinate transformation, whereas $\bar{\bar{g}}$ is the corresponding metric tensor, which is conveniently expressed as a linear combination of its different spectral components

$$\bar{\bar{g}} = \sum_{n=-3}^3 \bar{\bar{g}}_n e^{in\Omega t}$$

Considering an un-deformed isotropic medium, we can rewrite Maxwell's equations by applying the appropriate TO rules as

$$-\nabla \times \bar{\mathbf{E}} = \frac{\partial}{\partial t} (\bar{\bar{g}} \mu \bar{\mathbf{H}})$$

$$\nabla \times \bar{\mathbf{H}} = \frac{\partial}{\partial t} [\bar{\bar{g}} (\epsilon + \epsilon_0 \bar{\Delta} \epsilon) \bar{\mathbf{E}}] + \bar{\bar{g}} \sigma_e \bar{\mathbf{E}}$$

The above leads to a modified version of the Helmholtz's equation [8]

$$\begin{aligned} \nabla \times \bar{\mathbf{A}}^{-1} \nabla \times \mathbf{E}_1 - \omega_1^2 \bar{\mathbf{C}} \mathbf{E}_1 \\ = \omega_1^2 [\bar{\mathbf{K}} \mathbf{E}_1 + (\bar{\mathbf{D}} + \bar{\mathbf{L}}) \mathbf{E}_2] - i \omega_1 \nabla \times (\bar{\mathbf{A}}^{-1} \bar{\mathbf{B}} \mathbf{H}_2) \\ \nabla \times \bar{\mathbf{A}}^{-1} \nabla \times \mathbf{E}_2 - \omega_2^2 \bar{\mathbf{C}} \mathbf{E}_2 \\ = \omega_2^2 [(\bar{\mathbf{D}}^* + \bar{\mathbf{L}}^*) \mathbf{E}_1 + \bar{\mathbf{K}} \mathbf{E}_2] - i \omega_2 \nabla \times (\bar{\mathbf{A}}^{-1} \bar{\mathbf{B}}^* \mathbf{H}_1) \end{aligned}$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{\mathbf{A}} = \bar{\bar{g}}_0 \mu, \quad \bar{\mathbf{B}} = \bar{\bar{g}}_1 \mu, \quad \bar{\mathbf{C}} = \bar{\bar{g}}_0 \epsilon, \quad \bar{\mathbf{D}} = \bar{\bar{g}}_1 \epsilon, \quad \bar{\mathbf{K}} = \frac{\epsilon_0}{2} (\bar{\bar{g}}_1 \bar{\Delta} \epsilon^* + \bar{\bar{g}}_1^* \bar{\Delta} \epsilon) \\ \text{and } \bar{\mathbf{L}} = \frac{\epsilon_0}{2} (\bar{\bar{g}}_2 \bar{\Delta} \epsilon^* + \bar{\bar{g}}_2 \bar{\Delta} \epsilon). \end{aligned}$$

Upon comparison with the general form of Helmholtz equation, $\bar{\mathbf{A}}$ takes the place of $\bar{\bar{\mu}}_r$ and $\omega_n^2 \bar{\mathbf{C}}$ that of $k_0^2 [\bar{\bar{\epsilon}}_r - i \sigma_e / (\omega \epsilon_0)]$, whereas on the right hand side the source term take place.

Fig. 2. a) Optical contributions to the mechanical equation: E-field, b) electrostriction contributes in the volume $\mathbf{F}_{ES,V}(\frac{N}{m^3})$.

Figure 2 provides a numerical example of the force contribution $\mathbf{F}_{ES,V}$, defined in a simple optical cavity in which a TE-polarized mode is resonating.

III. CONCLUSION

Opto-mechanical coupling in micro- and nano-cavities could help in developing a new generation of microwave photonic devices with extremely small foot-print, sub-mW power consumption and tunable frequency. A rigorous modeling of the OM multiphysics problem is proposed to fully investigate the correlated phenomena. This kind of analysis could also help to explore the quantum world in a more convenient way. In particular, OM cavities may be used to test the ultimate limits of quantum physics when the entanglement of electromagnetic radiation and mechanical waves takes place.

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